

A Study of Humic Acid Synthesised in Presence of Clay Catalyst

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A humic acid sample was synthesised from glycine and hydroquinone in presence of a clay suspension used as a catalytic agent for oxidation. The synthetic acid has been characterised by electrometric titrations, viscosity determinations, visible and infrared spectroscopy with a view to probing its physicochemical properties. Attempts have also been made to correlate the results obtained from these experiments with the coiling-decoiling behaviour as well as the aliphatic-aromatic balance of the acid.

THE clay fraction of soil plays an important role in the *in situ* synthesis of humic materials in soils. In the present paper, we have examined such catalytic role of clay by way of synthesising a clay catalysed humic acid, a synthetic analogue of the humic acid of natural origin. The former has been used as a base material for studying the properties for the natural substances, which are of rather complex molecular nature and cannot be degraded to definite fractions usually.

The present study probes the properties of the clay-synthesised humic acid sample by way of conducting electrometric titrations (potentiometric and conductometric), viscometric measurements as well as visible and infrared spectroscopic investigations.

Experimental

Equal amounts (15 g) of hydroquinone and glycine were mixed with a sample (3.5 g) of oxide-free clay (isolated from 30–44 cm profile depth of Piyasal soil, District Purulia, West Bengal) in suspension on separate reaction vessels and the pH was adjusted to 8.0 by 0.1 N Ca(OH)₂ solution. The suspensions were placed in 500 ml conical flasks stoppered with cotton pads, followed by gentle shaking for a period of 20 days. The pH was maintained at 8.0 throughout the period by checking the same at an interval of three days. On the twentieth day, the contents of the flasks were filtered. The filtrate was acidified with 0.1 N HCl and the humic materials were precipitated. The precipitated humic materials were then dialysed to get the humic acid in H-form.

Potentiometric titration: Standard NaOH solution (0.1 N) was used for potentiometric titration. Carboxylic and phenolic OH group contents were computed from the acidity equivalents of the initial and final inflexion points of the titration curve¹. The amount of fresh alkali needed to attain a

stable higher pH, following a fall in the final pH (on standing after initial titration) as well as the time required for the same were also recorded for the sample.

Conductometric titration: Conductometric titration was carried out by using the same NaOH solution as used in potentiometry. The carboxylic and phenolic OH group contents were reckoned from the initial and final breaks of the titration curve.

Viscosity measurements: The viscosity of the HA suspension was measured (while rendering all the COOH groups to sodium carboxylate form) by using the Ubbelohde viscometer, having an average flow-time of 430.0 s for 11 ml of distilled water at 25°. The *A* and *B* coefficients of Jones-Doles' equation were obtained from the intercept and slope of the best-fit linear plot of $\eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C}$ vs $\sqrt{C}$ according to the equation,

$$\frac{\eta/\eta_0 - 1}{\sqrt{C}} = \eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where η_0 and η denote the viscosity coefficients at the same temperature of the solvent (water) and HA suspension, having a percentage concentration *C* respectively and *A* and *B* are the empirical constants sensitive to solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions respectively. The *B_{expt}* value of the humate anion was then obtained by using the literature value² of *B_{Na+}* as follows,

$$B_{expt} = B_{Na-HA} - B_{Na+}$$

The *B_{expt}* value was approximated to the corresponding intrinsic viscosity³, which was used to compute the molecular weight (*M*) from the modified Staudinger's equation⁴,

$$[\eta] = K(M)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

where, $K = 7.3 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\alpha = 0.65$.

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC INFORMATION ABOUT HA SAMPLE

Amount of carboxylic group meq g ⁻¹	Amount of phenolic (OH) group meq. g ⁻¹	pH at first inflection point (pH ₁)	pH at final inflection point (pH ₂)	Δ pH	Amount of fresh alkali required to stabilise at higher pH meq. g ⁻¹	Time required to stabilise at the higher pH h
1.12	2.89	6.9	8.9	4.45	6.65	94.0

TABLE 2—VISCOMETRIC INFORMATION ABOUT HA SAMPLE

Concn. (C) %	√C (percent) ^{1/2}	$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right) \sqrt{C}$ (percent) ^{-1/2}	B _{expt} of Na-humate (percent) ⁻¹ (B _{Na-HA})	B _{expt} of humate anion (percent) ⁻¹ (B _{HA} = B _{HA-Na} - B _{Na+})	Molecular weight (M)	Partial molar volume ($\bar{V}$) cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0.0148	0.1216	0.0499	0.3785	0.3410	12783	12.81
0.0297	0.1723	0.0752				
0.0595	0.2439	0.1253				
0.1190	0.3449	0.1929				

The partial molar volume of the sample was ascertained by fitting the density data of aqueous HA suspension to the following equation⁵,

$$\bar{V} = \frac{M}{1000 \left[\rho - \frac{d\rho}{dc} \times C \right]}$$

where, ρ is density of the suspension at concentration C , C the molar concentration of the HA suspension, and $d\rho/dc$ is slope of ρ vs C plots.

Visible spectrophotometry: By using a Systronics spectrophotometer, the optical densities at 465 and 665 nm for the HA suspension (Na-form) were noted at two different pH's, namely, 7.0 and 9.0.

Infrared spectroscopy: The ir spectrum (KBr) of the HA sample was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer fitted with a NaCl prism.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometry: Table 1 records the carboxylic and phenolic OH group contents and also $\Delta \text{pH} = \text{pH}_{3/4} - \text{pH}_{1/4}$, where $\text{pH}_{1/4}$ and $\text{pH}_{3/4}$ refer to the pH values corresponding to one-fourth and three-fourths of the final inflection point. The ΔpH value of the given HA sample being greater than 0.954 signifies the polyprotic nature of the humic acid sample⁶.

A substantial amount of fresh alkali (6.65 meq g⁻¹; Table 1) was needed to stabilise the higher pH of the given sample, indicating a considerable amount of remainder H⁺ ions which were not accessible to alkali initially. Table 1 also records the time (94 h) required to stabilise the higher pH depends on the ease of decoiling which is inversely related to the intramolecular H-bonding. This in turn, is governed by the steric hindrance associated with a particular conformation of the molecules due to their coiled shape.

Conductometry: The carboxylic and phenolic OH group contents were computed from the acidity equivalents of the initial and final breaks of the conductometric titration curve: amount of COOH group, 1.55 meq g⁻¹; amount of phenolic OH group, 2.43 meq g⁻¹; total acidity, 3.99 meq g⁻¹. The conductometric titration curve gives more or less similar information to the potentiometric curve.

Viscometry: Table 2 represents the variation of $\eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C}$ over a concentration range of 0.01–0.12%. The B value is approximated to the intrinsic viscosity of the HA sample, which gives a value of 12783 for the molecular weight of the polymer by the use of equation (2).

The partial molar volume of the HA sample (Table 2) indicates that a cavity of 12.81 ml is needed to hold one mole of the sample in aqueous medium.

Spectrophotometry: The spectrophotometric analyses data of the HA sample are as follows: E_A/E_0 values at pH 7.0 is 2.340 and at pH 9.0 is 2.244; $\Delta E_A/E_0$ value is 0.096. The E_A/E_0 values are greater than unity at both pH. This goes to establish that the absorbance by the aliphatic part is greater than that of the aromatic part due to a particular conformational arrangement of the aliphatic and aromatic moieties.

The positive value of $\Delta(E_A/E_0) = (E_A/E_0)_{\text{at pH 9.0}} - (E_A/E_0)_{\text{at pH 7.0}}$ signifies the fact that addition of alkali (NaOH) rendered HA molecules 'unfolded under thermodynamic compulsion'. At higher pH the hidden aromatic parts inside the coiled HA molecule get released which leads to a lowering of E_A/E_0 value giving a positive value of $\Delta(E_A/E_0)$. Thus the $\Delta(E_A/E_0)$ value may be regarded as an 'index of flexibility'.

Spectroscopy: The ir spectroscopic data (Table 3) as obtained from the frequency vs absorp-

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL DATA OF HA SAMPLE

$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments
3 600–3 100 (s, b)	Hydrogen-bonded phenolic OH. Partly NH stretching of free NH ₂ groups
1 700 (w)	C=O stretching of amides
1 610–1 570 (s, b)	C=O stretching of aromatic ketones, COOH group and C=C stretching of aromatic rings
1 500 (w)	C=C stretching of aromatic rings, OH bending of aliphatic OH ₂
1 400–1 360 (m)	CH bending of aliphatic CH ₂ and COO ⁻ stretching
1 050–1 000 (s, b)	C–O in cyclic and aliphatic esters and alcohols

tion plot show that the given HA sample contains several characteristic functional groups having different absorption bands. The principal characteristic features of humic acid spectrum are given by the strong absorption at around 3 600–3 100 cm⁻¹, which is assigned for the extensive H-bonding

in the humic acid sample. The absorption at around 1 610–1 570 cm⁻¹ registers that the HA sample is well-aromatised, which is in agreement with earlier reports by several workers^{1,8}.

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